

Type and level of production provided by the requestor

Type of production: broiler, duck, laying hen and turkey

Level: slaughter

Keywords: stunning

Background context provided by the requestor

We have observed challenges in assessing what constitutes an acceptable level of pre-stun shocks in waterbath stunning. Some of our slaughter facilities are experiencing issues in this regard. While we can determine that the occurrence of electrical shocks is too high in certain cases, it remains difficult to assess in a consistent manner when the corrective measures taken by the company are sufficient.

Question raised by the requestor

I would like to ask for your support in clarifying:

- Which indicators should be observed to identify pre-stun shocks,
- What are the main hazards are in relation to this issue, and
What preventive measures can be implemented to avoid or reduce their occurrence

Answer

Definition

Pre-stun shocks occur when a bird experiences electric shocks before losing consciousness during electrical waterbath stunning (WBS). This typically happens when a part of the bird's body other than the head (most often a wing) contacts the electrified water before the bird is effectively stunned or killed and the current passes through the body without affecting the brain (EFSA, 2019; DEFRA, 2007; Rao et al., 2013).

Pre-stun shocks cause severe pain and distress before loss of consciousness and may trigger vigorous wing flapping or withdrawal reactions that can prevent the head from fully contacting with the electrified water and therefore the head to be stimulated. Furthermore, as a result, birds may not be effectively stunned and can reach the neck-cutting area while still conscious (EFSA, 2019; Contreras-Jodar et al., 2022). The wing flapping triggered by pre-stun shocks can also cause vicious cycles of wing flapping causing additional shocks to neighboring birds. Moreover, intense flapping can lead to physical injuries and carcass damage, such as red wing tips, hemorrhages in wings and fillets, and broken pectoral bones (Riggs, 2022).

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Indicators to assess pre-stun shocks:

Animal-Based Indicators (ABIs): Birds are considered to be experiencing pre-stun shocks when one or more of these behavioral indicators are observed when contacting the WB.

- **Vigorous wing flapping:** Continuous, rapid wing movements (Riggs, 2022; EFSA, 2019).
- **Withdrawal reactions of wings or head:** Quick avoiding movements like muscle contraction of the neck, head, or wings.
- **Vocalisations:** single or repeated short, loud, high-pitched screams. (Riggs, 2022).
- **Carcass damage indicators** include red wing tips, hemorrhages in wings and fillets, and broken pectoral bones caused by flapping (Riggs, 2022).

The validity of these ABIs is high, but their feasibility depends on the waterbath design and the inspector's ability to observe the birds at the point of entry. Therefore, depending on the slaughterhouse setup, the feasibility can vary from low to high (EURCAW, 2020). However, even in situations where direct observation is challenging, the assessment of pre-stun shocks should still be prioritized using ABIs. Only when the assessment of ABIs is not feasible should inspectors rely on resource-based indicators (EFSA, 2019).

Resource-Based Indicators (RBIs):

- **Design and construction of the shackle line and ramp** (EFSA, 2019): Proper design should ensure the bird's head is the first body part to contact the electrified water and that the movement of the birds along the line is smooth to prevent flapping. This can be achieved preventing any curves, inclines, drops, or abrupt transitions near the entrance to the waterbath. The ramp leading to the waterbath should have a smooth, steep incline, ensuring a smooth, gradual ascent to the entrance. Additionally, the ramp should be electrically insulated and no water from the waterbath should be running down it (HSA, 2016). Additionally, shackles must be appropriately sized for the species and size of the bird. They should feature multiple slots with varying taper gauges to minimize leg compression (HSA, 2016). Furthermore, live bird shackling should incorporate calming measures, such as dim blue lighting or breast comforters (e.g., breast contact strips or breast contact conveyors for heavier birds, such as large turkeys). Feasibility and reliability of these indicators are high, although validity depends on their correlation with ABIs (EURCAW, 2020).

Management-Based Indicators (MBIs):

- Records of equipment maintenance frequency.
- Certificates of competence and evidence of staff training.
- Existence of standard operating procedures (SOPs) for monitoring pre-stun shocks.

These indicators are feasible and reliable but have low validity, as documentation and training do not guarantee that operators correctly apply stunning procedures in practice (EURCAW, 2020).

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Hazards

Several hazards increase the risk of pre-stun shocks:

- The wings, especially when held open or flapping, are particularly vulnerable as the carpometacarpus may contact electrified water (Riggs, 2022).
- Species with large wingspans, such as geese and turkeys, are at higher risk due to wings hanging below the head when suspended upside down (Riggs, 2022).
- Agitated or struggling birds increase the chance of wing contact with the current (Riggs, 2022).
- Contact between legs or feet and grounded rubbing bars near the waterbath entrance can cause shocks if electrical isolation is inadequate or if live water overflows the ramp (Riggs, 2022; EFSA, 2019).
- Improperly sized shackles can cause pain and tissue damage by compressing the shank.
- Gradual descent of the shackle line and premature contact of the beak can cause initial shocks followed by rigidity and head lifting, potentially leading to repeated shocks even after proper immersion (Riggs, 2022).

Preventive and Corrective Measures

No bird should receive pre-stun shocks; if they do, corrective and preventive measures should be implemented. Preventing pre-stun shocks might require the following interventions:

- Calming birds and reducing wing flapping through environmental management such as low lighting, breast rubs, smooth transition into the waterbath, and gentle shackling (EFSA, 2019).
- Proper waterbath design, including non-conductive entrances and electrically insulated ramps, can minimize live water overflow and pre-stun shocks (AVMA, 2024; HSA, 2016).
- Maintaining optimal water levels to immerse birds up to the base of their wings (EFSA, 2019).
- In low-throughput plants, installing sensing devices that activate the current only when the head of the birds are fully immersed until the base of the wing (Fuseini, 2023).
- In high-throughput plants, using steep, extended ramps at the waterbath entrance ensures the bird's head and wings enter first, reducing the risk of premature contact (Fuseini, 2023; Riggs, 2022).
- Monitoring for sudden distress behaviors along the shackle line to identify hazards for pre-stun shocks (Riggs, 2022).
- Prompt reporting to Animal Welfare Officers or veterinarians for investigation and corrective action when pre-stun shocks are suspected (Riggs, 2022).

It is important to note that no corrective measure exists once a pre-stun shock has occurred (EFSA, 2019).

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